

***THE ROLE OF AUDIT REPORT LATE IN MEDIATING THE
EFFECT OF CORPORATE GOVERNANCE MECHANISM,
AUDIT FEE AND LITIGATION ON VALUE CREATION***

DISERTATION

BY:

NAWANG KALBUANA

NIM :7783220004

**DOCTORAL PROGRAMME IN ACCOUNTING
FACULTY OF ECONOMICS AND BUSINESS
SULTAN AGENG TIRTAYASA UNIVERSITY
SERANG-BANTEN**

2024

**PERAN *AUDIT REPORT LATE* DALAM MEMEDIASI
PENGARUH *CORPORATE GOVERNANCE MECHANISM*,
AUDIT FEE DAN LITIGASI TERHADAP *VALUE CREATION***

DISERTASI

Oleh :

NAWANG KALBUANA

NIM :7783220004

PROGRAM STUDI DOKTOR ILMU AKUNTANSI

FAKULTAS EKONOMI DAN BISNIS

UNIVERSITAS SULTAN AGENG TIRTAYASA

SERANG-BANTEN

2024

ABSTRACT

This study aims to provide empirical evidence on the influence of audit fees, corporate governance mechanisms (independent commissioners, independent audit committees), and litigation on audit report late and value creation, and to evaluate the role of audit report late in mediating these influences on value creation.

The research method used is a quantitative approach with panel data analysis, involving companies that experienced delays in submitting audit financial reports and received Warning Letters from the Financial Services Authority (OJK) from 2018 to 2023. Multiple regression analysis was applied to examine the relationship between the independent variables with audit report late and value creation.

The research findings show that audit fees significantly positively affect audit report late, indicating that high audit fees are often associated with report delays. In contrast, independent commissioners significantly negatively affect audit reports late, indicating that their presence accelerates audit completion. However, independent audit committees do not show a significant effect on audit report late. Litigation is shown to have a positive influence on audit report late, as a result of legal risks that require a more detailed audit.

In terms of value creation, audit fees, independent commissioners, and independent audit committees do not show a significant effect, while litigation also does not affect value creation directly. However, audit report late has a significant positive effect on value creation, indicating that audit report lateness may reflect a

commitment to the quality of information that supports firm value. Audit report late does not significantly mediate the relationship between audit fee and value creation, as well as between independent audit committee and value creation. However, audit report late mediates the relationship between independent commissioners and value creation negatively, and between litigation and value creation significantly.

The results of this study provide deep insight into the dynamics between audit fees, corporate governance mechanisms, litigation, and audit report late on value creation. The findings enrich agency theory and provide practical guidance and policy considerations for audit management and corporate governance.

Keywords: audit fee, corporate governance mechanism, litigation, audit report late, value creation.

REFERENCES

- Ado, A. B., Rashid, N., Mustapha, U. A., & Ademola, L. S. (2020). The Impact Of Audit Quality On The Financial Performance Of Listed Companies Nigeria. *Journal of Critical Reviews*, 7(9), 37–42.
- Afify, H. A. E. (2009). Determinants of audit report lag: Does implementing corporate governance have any impact? Empirical evidence from Egypt. *Journal of Applied Accounting Research*, 10(1), 56–86. <https://doi.org/10.1108/09675420910963397>
- Afriat, H., Dvir-Gvirsman, S., Tsuriel, K., & Ivan, L. (2020). “This is capitalism. It is not illegal”: Users’ attitudes toward institutional privacy following the Cambridge Analytica scandal. *Information Society*, 37(2), 115–127. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01972243.2020.1870596>
- Agarwal, S., & Kapoor, R. (2023). Value Creation Tradeoff in Business Ecosystems: Leveraging Complementarities While Managing Interdependencies. *Organization Science*, 34(3), 1216–1242. <https://doi.org/10.1287/orsc.2022.1615>
- Agyei-Mensah, B. K. (2018). Impact of corporate governance attributes and financial reporting lag on corporate financial performance. *African Journal of Economic and Management Studies*, 9(3), 349–366. <https://doi.org/10.1108/AJEMS-08-2017-0205>
- Ahmet, S., Halil, E. I., & Burcu, B. (2022). How Important is Corporate Governance Features and the Lags on Audit Reports in Firm Performance: The Case of Turkey. *Studies in Business and Economics*, 17(1), 218–237. <https://doi.org/10.2478/sbe-2022-0015>
- Aisyah, S. (2022). The Role of Financial Performance as a Mediator Between Good Corporate Governance and Firm Value. *Atestasi: Jurnal Ilmiah Akuntansi*, 5(1), 255–268. <https://doi.org/10.57178/atestasi.v5i1.312>
- Al-Araj, R. (2023). Characteristics of ACs and their impact on the period of issuing the auditor’s report: An Empirical study on Jordanian public shareholding companies. *Uncertain Supply Chain Management*, 11(2), 503–512. <https://doi.org/10.5267/j.uscm.2023.2.014>
- Amar, W. Ben, Boujenoui, A., & Francoeur, C. (2011). CEO attributes, board composition, and acquirer value creation: A Canadian study. *Canadian Journal of Administrative Sciences*, 28(4), 480–492. <https://doi.org/10.1002/CJAS.223>
- Ameels, A., Bruggeman, W., & Scheipers, G. (2002). Value-based Management Control Processes to Create Value through Integration - A literature Review. *Recent Trends in Valuation: From Strategy to Value*, (18), 87–150.
- Anwar, R., Suleman, N., & Thalib, M. (2022). Size board of commissioners, independent commissioners and audit Committee on Audit Report Lag. *Golden Ratio of Auditing Research*, 2, 1. <https://doi.org/10.52970/grar.v2i1>.
- Arhinful, R., & Radmehr, M. (2023). The effect of financial leverage on financial performance: evidence from non-financial institutions listed on the Tokyo stock market. *Journal of Capital Markets Studies*, 7(1), 53–71.

- <https://doi.org/10.1108/jcms-10-2022-0038>
- Ariani, D. I. R., & Agustia, D. (2020). The impacts of good corporate governance on corporate performance with corporate social responsibility disclosure as the intervening variable. *International Journal of Innovation, Creativity and Change*, 11(9), 280–299. <https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85082194450&partnerID=40&md5=56ec2fd5906cbb9ce6e57f5ac48fe1ec>
- Arora, A. (2022). Female Leadership and Firm Value in an Emerging Economy: A Panel Data Framework. *Vision*, 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.1177/09722629221101153>
- Ashton, R. H., Willingham, J. J., & Elliott, R. K. (1987). An Empirical Analysis of Audit Delay Journal. *Journal of Accounting Research*, 25(2), 275–292.
- Aviantara, R. (2023). Scoring the financial distress and the financial statement fraud of Garuda Indonesia with «DDCC» as the financial solutions. *Journal of Modelling in Management*, 18(1), 1–16. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JM2-01-2020-0017>
- Azzuhri, A. A., Syarafina, A., Yoga, F. T., & Amalia, R. (2018). A Creative, Innovative, and Solutive Transportation for Indonesia with Its Setbacks and How to Tackle Them: A Case Study of the Phenomenal GOJEK. *Review of Integrative Business and Economics Research*, 7(1), 59–67. <http://buscompress.com/journal-home.html>
- Bank Indonesia, G. (2006). Peraturan Bank Indonesia Nomor 8/4/PBI/2006 tentang Pelaksanaan Good Corporate Governance Bagi Bank Umum. *Bank Indonesia Nomor 8/4/PBI/2006*, 1–30.
- Baron, R. M., & Kenny, D. A. (1986). The Moderator-Mediator Variable Distinction in Social Psychological Research. Conceptual, Strategic, and Statistical Considerations. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 51(6), 1173–1182. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0022-3514.51.6.1173>
- Binti Hashim, U. J., & Abdul Rahman, R. B. (2012). Internal corporate governance mechanisms and audit report lag: A study of Malaysian listed companies. *Corporate Board: Role, Duties and Composition*, 8(3), 48–63. <https://doi.org/10.22495/cbv8i3art4>
- Buachoom, W. W., & Amornkitvikai, Y. (2022). The Moderating Effects of Board Independence and the Separation of Chairman–Chief Executive Officer Duality Roles on a Firm’s Value: Evidence from the Thai Listed Firms. *Global Business Review*. <https://doi.org/10.1177/09721509221119705>
- Buallay, A., Hamdan, A., & Zureigat, Q. (2017). Corporate governance and firm performance: evidence from Saudi Arabia. *Australasian Accounting, Business and Finance Journal*, 11(1), 78–98. <https://doi.org/10.14453/aabfj.v11i1.6>
- Budisantoso, T., & Kurniawan, H. (2024). The contagion effect of decreasing audit’s quality on financial statement audit engagement: the Indonesian case. *Asia-Pacific Journal of Business Administration*, 16(1), 63–76. <https://doi.org/10.1108/APJBA-11-2020-0393>
- Carcello, J. V., & Palmrose, Z.-V. (1994). Auditor litigation and modified reporting on bankrupt clients. *Journal of Accounting Research*, 32(May 2023), 1–30.
- Chapman, K., Drake, M., Schroeder, J. H., & Seidel, T. (2023). Earnings

- announcement delays and implications for the auditor-client relationship. *Review of Accounting Studies*, 28(1), 45–90. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11142-021-09635-3>
- Chen, C, Jia, H., Xu, Y., & Ziebart, D. (2022). The effect of audit firm attributes on audit delay in the presence of financial reporting complexity. *Managerial Auditing Journal*, 37(2), 283–302. <https://doi.org/10.1108/MAJ-12-2020-2969>
- Chen, Chu, Jia, H., Xu, Y., & Ziebart, D. (2022). The effect of audit firm attributes on audit delay in the presence of financial reporting complexity. *Managerial Auditing Journal*, 37(2), 283–302. <https://doi.org/10.1108/MAJ-12-2020-2969>
- Chen, L., Yuan, T., Cebula, R. J., Shuangjin, W., & Foley, M. (2021). Fulfillment of esg responsibilities and firm performance: a zero-sum game or mutually beneficial. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 13(19). <https://doi.org/10.3390/su131910954>
- Chen, Y. M., Liu, H. H., Liu, Y. S., & Huang, H. T. (2016). A preemptive power to offensive patent litigation strategy: Value creation, transaction costs and organizational slack. *Journal of Business Research*, 69(5), 1634–1638. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2015.10.030>
- Craswell, A., Stokes, D. J., & Laughton, J. (2002). Auditor independence and fee dependence. *Journal of Accounting and Economics*, 33(2), 253–275. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0165-4101\(02\)00044-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0165-4101(02)00044-7)
- DeAngelo, L. E. (1981). Auditor size and audit fees. *Journal of Accounting and Economics*, 3(3), 183–199.
- Durand, G. (2019). The determinants of audit report lag: a meta-analysis. *Managerial Auditing Journal*, 34(1), 44–75. <https://doi.org/10.1108/MAJ-06-2017-1572>
- Durrand, G. (2018). The determinants of audit report lag: a meta-analysis. *Managerial Auditing Journal*, 34(1), 1–5.
- Dwiyani, T., Purnomo, & Darmanto. (2020). Debt on asset ratio, return on asset and audit opinion toward return share with the intervening audit delay. *International Journal of Economics, Business and Accounting Research (IJEBAR)*, 4(1).
- Eisenhardt, K. M. (1989). Agency theory: An assessment and review. *Academy of Management Review*, 14(1), 57–74.
- Elitzur, R., & Falk, H. (1996). Planned audit quality. *Journal of Accounting and Public Policy*, 15(3), 247–269. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0278-4254\(96\)00024-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/0278-4254(96)00024-5)
- Fama, E. F. (1978). The Effects of a Firm's Investment and Financing Decisions on the Welfare of Its Security Holders. *The American Economic Review*, 68(3), 272–284.
- Fama, E. F., & French, K. R. (1998). Taxes, financing decisions, and firm value. *Journal of Finance*, 53(3), 819–843. <https://doi.org/10.1111/0022-1082.00036>
- Fama, E., & Jensen, M. C. (1983). Separation of Ownership and Control. *The Journal of Law and Economics*, 26, 301–325. <https://doi.org/10.1086/467037>
- Fauziah, N., & Setiawati, E. (2023). The effect of auditor fees, audit opinions, audit

- tenure, profitability and company size on audit delay. *International Journal of Latest Research in Humanities and Social Science (IJLRHSS)*, 06(05), 81–89.
- Ferguson, A., & Stokes, D. (2010). Brand Name Audit Pricing, Industry Specialization, and Leadership Premiums post-Big 8 and Big 6 Mergers. *Contemporary Accounting Research*, 19(1), 111–116. <https://doi.org/10.1506/30f8-3mch-wv7b-2cgv>
- Ferriswara, D., Sayidah, N., & Buniarto, E. A. (2022). Do corporate governance , capital structure predict financial performance and firm value?(empirical study of Jakarta Islamic index). *Cogent Business and Management*, 9(1). <https://doi.org/10.1080/23311975.2022.2147123>
- Gede, W. A. A., & Ratna, S. M. M. (2021). The effect of gender of the audit committee, audit committee meetings, audit committee independence, independent commissioners and institutional ownership on audit delay. *Eurasia: Economics & Business*, 1(43), 5–24.
- Ghardallou, W. (2023). The heterogeneous effect of leverage on firm performance: a quantile regression analysis. *International Journal of Islamic and Middle Eastern Finance and Management*, 16(1), 210–225. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IMEFM-12-2021-0490>
- Grimaldi, M., Cricelli, L., & Rogo, F. (2012). A methodology to assess value creation in communities of innovation. *Journal of Intellectual Capital*, 13(3), 305–330. <https://doi.org/10.1108/14691931211248882>
- Hall, J. H. (2015). International Journal of Productivity and Performance Management. *International Journal of Productivity and Performance Management*, 64(8), 1–49. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1108/IJPPM-08-2016-0178>
- Hall, J. H. (2018). Value creation measures: an industry-based study. *International Journal of Productivity and Performance Management*, 67(2), 426–444. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJPPM-08-2016-0178>
- Handayani, B. D., Rohman, A., Chariri, A., & Pamungkas, I. D. (2020). Corporate financial performance on corporate governance mechanism and corporate value: Evidence from Indonesia. *Montenegrin Journal of Economics*, 16(3), 161–171. <https://doi.org/10.14254/1800-5845/2020.16-3.13>
- Handayani, Y. D., & Yustikasari, Y. (2017). Corporate Governance and Audit Report Lags at Manufacturing Companies in the Industrial Sector of Consumption Goods. *European Journal of Business and Management*, 9(29), 24–32. www.iiste.org
- Harjoto, M. A., & Laksmana, I. (2023). The impact of COVID-19 restrictions on audit fees and audit delay: evidence from auditor local offices. *Managerial Auditing Journal*. <https://doi.org/10.1108/MAJ-03-2022-3487>
- He, H., & Shi, W. (2023). Enterprise litigation risk and enterprise performance. *Finance Research Letters*, (April), 1–8. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.frl.2023.103783>
- Hidayati, N. D. (2011). Pattern of corporate social responsibility programs: A case study. *Social Responsibility Journal*, 7(1), 104–117. <https://doi.org/10.1108/174711111111114576>
- Hoitash, R., Markelevich, A., & Barragato, C. A. (2007). Auditor fees and audit

- quality. *Managerial Auditing Journal*, 22(8), 761–786. <https://doi.org/10.1108/02686900710819634>
- Hossain, M. K., Islam, M. S., & Reza, M. M. (2022). Do Corporate Governance Mechanisms Truly Act As The Drivers Of Shareholder Value In The Banking Sector In Bangladesh ? Evidence From The Economic Profit Perspective. *International Journal of Business and Society*, 23(2), 1005–1024.
- Huang, X., & Kang, F. (2022). Do high-reputation companies pay more non-audit fees? *Accounting Research Journal*, 35(2), 145–159. <https://doi.org/10.1108/ARJ-07-2020-0171>
- IAPI. (2016). Peraturan Pengurus Nomor 2 Tahun 2016 Tentang Penentuan Imbalan Jasa Audit Laporan Keuangan. *Jurnal Ekonomi Modernisasi*, Vol. 14, pp. 177–194.
- Indriastuti, M., Winarsih, & Najihah, N. (2021). Information disclosure on good corporate governance and corporate social responsibility as determinants of firm value (B. L., P.-M. A., & E. T., Eds.). 14th International Conference on Complex, Intelligent and Software Intensive Systems, CISIS 2020, Held in Conjunction with the 14th International Conference on Innovative Mobile and Internet Services in Ubiquitous Computing, *IMIS 2020*, pp. 375–382. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-50454-0_36
- Itan, I., & Antoni, A. (2021). Does Corporate Governance Influence Value Creation : Assessing the Mediating Role of Csr and Tax Avoidance. *Jurnal Ekonomi Balance*, 17(2), 301–316. <https://doi.org/10.26618/jeb.v17i2.6077>
- Jia, N., Shi, J., & Wang, Y. (2018). Value creation and value capture in governing shareholder relationships: Evidence from a policy experiment in an emerging market. *Strategic Management Journal*, 39(9), 2466–2488. <https://doi.org/10.1002/smj.2921>
- Johnson, L. E. (1998). Further evidence on the determinants of local government audit delay. *Journal of Public Budgeting, Accounting & Financial Management*, 10(3).
- Kalash, I. (2023). The financial leverage–financial performance relationship in the emerging market of Turkey: the role of financial distress risk and currency crisis. *EuroMed Journal of Business*, 18(1), 1–20. <https://doi.org/10.1108/EMJB-04-2021-0056>
- Kaprowski, W. R., Arsenault, S. J., & Cipriano, M. (2010). Financial statement reporting of pending litigation : attorneys, auditors, and difference of opinions. *Fordham Journal of Corporate & Financial Law*, 15(2).
- Kartika, I., Sulistyowati, S., Septiawan, B., & Indriastuti, M. (2022). Corporate governance and non-performing loans: The mediating role of financial performance. *Cogent Business and Management*, 9(1). <https://doi.org/10.1080/23311975.2022.2126123>
- Khamainy, A. H., Ali, M., & Setiawan, M. A. (2022). Detecting financial statement fraud through new fraud diamond model: the case of Indonesia. *Journal of Financial Crime*, 29(3), 925–941. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JFC-06-2021-0118>
- Khan, A. W., & Subhan, Q. A. (2019). Impact of board diversity and audit on firm performance. *Cogent Business & Management*, 6(01), 1–16. <https://doi.org/10.1080/23311975.2019.1611719>

- Khasharmeh, H. A., & Aljifri, K. (2010). The timeliness of annual report in bahrain and the united arab emirates; an empirical comparative study. *The International Journal of Business and Finance Research*, 4(1), 335–366. <https://doi.org/10.1515/9781685856953-017>
- Krishnan, J., & Krishnan, J. (1997). Litigation Risk and Auditor Resignations. *The Accounting Review*, 72(4), 539–560.
- Kumar, K. K., & Vijayan, V. (2018). Value Creation Measurements : An Industry Based Study in India. *International Journal of Science and Research (IJSR)*, 8(4), 1120–1123.
- Kwak, J., & Park, M. (2020). Effect of Auditor ' s Simultaneous Audit and Tax Services and Tax-service Fee on Firm Value : Korea ' s Evidence. *Journal of Asian Finance, Economics and Business*, 7(7), 219–228. <https://doi.org/10.13106/jafeb.2020.vol7.no7.219>
- Lajmi, A., & Yab, M. (2022). The impact of internal corporate governance mechanisms on audit report lag: evidence from Tunisian listed companies. *EuroMed Journal of Business*, 17(4), 619–633. <https://doi.org/10.1108/EMJB-05-2021-0070>
- Larasati, D. A., Ratri, M. C., & Nasih, M. (2019). Cogent Business & Management Independent audit committee , risk management committee , and audit fees Independent audit committee , risk management committee , and audit fees. *Cogent Business & Management*, 00(00). <https://doi.org/10.1080/23311975.2019.1707042>
- Leditho, M. D., Kusumastati, W. W., & Safiq, M. (2023). Do company performance, multinational company, and audit fee affect audit delay? *Journal of Applied Accounting and Finance*, 7(1), 13–27.
- Lee, H.-Y., & Jahng, G.-J. (2008). Determinants of audit report lag: evidence from Korea - an examination of auditor related factors. *The Journal of Applied Business Research*, 24(2), 27–44.
- Leventis, S., Weetman, P., & Caramanis, C. (2005). Determinants of audit report lag: some evidence from the Athens stock exchange. *International Journal of Auditing*, 9(1), 45–58. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1099-1123.2005.00101.x>
- Lidyah, R., Mismiwati, Hartini, T., Akbar, D. A., Africano, F., & Anggreni, M. (2020). The Effect of Audit Committee, Independent Commissioners Board And Firm Size on Audit Delay Through Capital Structure as An Intervening Variable In Sharia Bank. *PalArch's Journal of Archaeology of Egypt/Egyptology*, 17(7), 11313–11325.
- Liu, H., Cullinan, C., & Zhang, J. (2021). Litigation against clients and audit report lag: an examination of the role of state ownership and regional legal development in China. *Managerial Auditing Journal*, 36(5), 744–769. <https://doi.org/10.1108/MAJ-02-2020-2557>
- Lu, H., & Wang, L. (2022). Risk Analysis of Enterprises' Investment in Infrastructure in Developing Countries Based on Structural Equation Model. *Mobile Information Systems*, 2022. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2022/4790726>
- Lumapow, L. S. (2018). The Influence of Managerial Ownership and Firm Size On Debt Policy. *International Journal of Applied Business & International Management*, 3(1), 305–360. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/0304->

405X(76)90026-X

- Lys, T., & Watts, R. L. (1994). Lawsuits against auditors. *Journal of Accounting Research*, 32(May 2023), 65–93.
- Mali, S., Rakocevic, S. B., & Savoju, G. (2012). Value creation through restructuring - key value drivers and value creation models. *Organizacija i Kierowanie*, 2012(4).
- Malm, J., Soyeh, K. W., & Kanuri, S. (2023). Journal of Behavioral and Experimental Finance Litigation risk and corporate performance. *Journal of Behavioral and Experimental Finance*, 37, 100725. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbef.2022.100725>
- Martinez, A. L., & Arquimedes de Jesus Moraes. (2014). Association between independent auditor fees and firm value: a study of Brazilian public companies. *Journal of Modern Accounting and Auditing*, 10(4), 442–450.
- Masulis, R. W., & Korwar, A. N. (1986). Seasoned equity offerings. *Journal of Financial Economics*, 15, 91–118.
- Masyitah, Z., Azhar, I., & Meutia, T. (2022). Pengaruh audit tenure dan penerapan IFRS terhadap keterlambatan penyampaian laporan keuangan dengan audit report lag sebagai pemediasi. *Jurnal Mahasiswa Akuntansi Samudra*, 3(5), 254–268. <https://doi.org/10.33059/jmas.v3i5.6318>
- McTaggart, J. M., Kontes, P. W., & Mankins, M. C. (1994). *The value imperative : managing for superior shareholder returns*. Maxwell Macmillan Canada.
- Modigliani, F., & Miller, M. H. (1958). The cost of capital, corporation finance and the theory of investment. *The American Economic Review*, 48(3), 261–297. <https://doi.org/10.1257/aer.103.7.i>
- Mohammed, N. F., Sutainim, N. A., Islam, M. S., & Mohamed, N. (2021). Integrated thinking, earnings manipulation and value creation: Malaysian empirical evidence. *Business Process Management Journal*, 27(4), 1179–1199. <https://doi.org/10.1108/BPMJ-06-2020-0261>
- Moutinho, V., Cerqueira, A., & Brandão, E. (2012). Audit Fees and Firm Performance. *Papers.Ssrn.Com*. <https://doi.org/http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.2180020>
- Muhammad, M. I. (2020). Effects of auditor attributes on audit reporting lag: empirical evidence from nigerian service firm. *Asian Journal of Empirical Research*, 10(4), 127–136. <https://doi.org/10.18488/journal.1007/2020.10.4/1007.4.127.136>
- Narang, S., & Kaur, M. (2014). Impact of Firm-specific Attributes on Shareholder Value Creation of Indian Companies: An Empirical Analysis. *Global Business Review*, 15(4), 847–866. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0972150914543422>
- Narcisa, A. (2016). The Influence of the Corporate Governance Mechanisms and Audit Fees on the Financial Performance Measured With ROA. *Annals of the „Constantin Brâncuși” University of Târgu Jiu, Economy Series*, (5), 20–31.
- Nindita, C., & Siregar, S. V. (2013). Analisis Pengaruh Ukuran Kantor Akuntan Publik Terhadap Kualitas Audit di Indonesia. *Jurnal Akuntansi Dan Keuangan*, 14(2). <https://doi.org/10.9744/jak.14.2.91-104>
- Nurwahyudi, M. R., & Mudasetia. (2020). Pengaruh Gender Wanita Dalam Dewan Direksi Terhadap Kinerja Keuangan Studi Pada Perusahaan Yang Masuk

- Index Kompas 100 Tahun 2014-2015. *Jurnal STIE Semarang (Edisi Elektronik)*, 12(2), 106–127.
- O’Sullivan, N. (2000). The impact of board composition and ownership on audit quality: Evidence from large UK companies. *British Accounting Review*, 32(4), 397–414. <https://doi.org/10.1006/bare.2000.0139>
- Oradi, J. (2021). CEO succession origin, audit report lag, and audit fees: Evidence from Iran. *Journal of International Accounting, Auditing and Taxation*, 45(xxxx), 100414. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.intaccudtax.2021.100414>
- Otoritas Jasa Keuangan. (2014). *Peraturan Otoritas Jasa Keuangan Nomor 33/POJK.04/2014 Tentang Direksi dan Dewan Komisaris Emiten Atau Perusahaan Publik*. [https://www.ojk.go.id/id/regulasi/Documents/Pages/POJK-tentang-Direksi-dan-Dewan--Komisaris-Emiten-atau-Perusahaan-Publik/POJK_33_Direksi dan Dewan Komisaris Emiten Atau Perusahaan Publik.pdf](https://www.ojk.go.id/id/regulasi/Documents/Pages/POJK-tentang-Direksi-dan-Dewan--Komisaris-Emiten-atau-Perusahaan-Publik/POJK_33_Direksi%20dan%20Dewan%20Komisaris%20Emiten%20Atau%20Perusahaan%20Publik.pdf)
- Oware, K. M., & Mallikarjunappa, T. (2019). Corporate social responsibility investment, third-party assurance and firm performance in India: The moderating effect of financial leverage. *South Asian Journal of Business Studies*, 8(3), 303–324. <https://doi.org/10.1108/SAJBS-08-2018-0091>
- Palmrose, Z.-V. (1986). Audit Fees and Auditor Size: Further Evidence. *Journal of Accounting Research*, 24(1), 97. <https://doi.org/10.2307/2490806>
- Palmrose, Z.-V. (1988). An analysis of auditor litigation and audit service quality. *The Accounting Review*, 63(1), 55–73.
- Panda, B., & Leepsa, N. M. (2017). Agency theory: Review of theory and evidence on problems and perspectives. *Indian Journal of Corporate Governance*, 10(1), 74–95. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0974686217701467>
- Parkash, M., Singhal, R., & Zhu, Y. (2022). The impact of loan covenants on audit delays and audit fees. *Journal of Corporate Accounting and Finance*, 33(4), 39–51. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jcaf.22561>
- Prasetyo, I., Aliyyah, N., Rusdiyanto, R., Nartasari, D. R., Nugroho, S., Rahmawati, Y., ... Rochman, A. S. (2021). What Affects Audit Delay in Indonesia? *Academy of Entrepreneurship Journal*, 27, 1–15.
- Pratt, J., & Stice, J. D. (1994). Audit Evidence , and Recommended Audit Fees The Effects of Client Characteristics on Auditor Litigation Risk Judgments , Required Audit Evidence , and Recommended Audit Fees. *The Accounting Review*, 69(4), 639–656.
- Pulic, A. (2004). Intellectual capital – does it create or destroy value? *Measuring Business Excellence*, 8(1), 62–68. <https://doi.org/10.1108/13683040410524757>
- Purbawangsa, I. B. A., Solimun, S., Fernandes, A. A. R., & Mangesti Rahayu, S. (2020). Corporate governance, corporate profitability toward corporate social responsibility disclosure and corporate value (comparative study in Indonesia, China and India stock exchange in 2013-2016). *Social Responsibility Journal*, 16(7), 983–999. <https://doi.org/10.1108/SRJ-08-2017-0160>
- Rahmatika, M. W., Widarjo, W., & Payamta, P. (2019). Peran Komisaris Independen dan Komite Audit dalam Meningkatkan Kinerja Keuangan Perusahaan Wholesale dan Retail Trade di Indonesia. *Jurnal Akuntansi Dan*

- Bisnis*, 19(1), 54. <https://doi.org/10.20961/jab.v19i1.384>
- Rusmanto, T., & Herlina, M. (2020). The connection between corporate governance and audit report lag: an Indonesian case. *American International Journal of Business Management (AIJBM)*, 3(8), 67–73. www.aijbm.com
- Saepudin, M. T., Gagah, E., & Amboningtyas, D. (2020). Analysis of The Effect of Good Corporate Governance, Liquidity, and Capital Structure on Company Value With Financial Performance as intervening Variables. *Journal of Management*, 6(1).
- Sahla, W. A., & Ardianto, A. (2023). Ethical values and auditors fraud tendency perception: testing of fraud pentagon theory. *Journal of Financial Crime*, 30(4), 966–982. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JFC-04-2022-0086>
- Santos, C., Cerqueira, A., & Brandao, E. (2015). Audit Fees , Non-Audit Fees and Corporate Performance. *FEP-UP, School of Economic and Management, University of Porto*, (December), 1–27. <http://ideas.repec.org/PaperSeries.html>
- Santosa, S., Ismail, T., Hanifah, I. A., & Muchlish, M. (2023). Intellectual Capital Measurement Revisited: Bibliometric Analysis of Value-Added Intellectual Coefficient. *Quality - Access to Success*, 24(194), 333–344. <https://doi.org/10.47750/QAS/24.194.37>
- Sari, R. C., Sholihin, M., Zuhrohtun, Z., Purnama, I. A., Dewanti, P. W., & Udhma, U. S. (2023). Why are not men and women more alike? Gender and clawbacks in the trade-off between accrual and real activity earnings manipulation. *Gender in Management*, 38(8), 1117–1134. <https://doi.org/10.1108/GM-06-2022-0203>
- Sayyar, H., Basiruddin, R., Zaleha, S., Rasid, A., & Elhabib, M. A. (2015). The Impact of Audit Quality on Firm Performance: Evidence from Malaysia. *Journal of Advanced Review on Scientific Research*, 10(1), 1–19.
- Sekaran, U., & Bougie, R. (2016). *Research methods for business*.
- Setia Atmaja, L. Y. (2009). Governance mechanisms and firm value: The impact of ownership concentration and dividends. *Corporate Governance: An International Review*, 17(6), 694–709. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-8683.2009.00768.x>
- Setiawan, G., & Nahumury, J. (2014). The effect of board of commissioners, audit committee, and stock ownership concentration on audit report lag of banking companies in Indonesia Stock Exchange. *The Indonesian Accounting Review*, 4(01), 15. <https://doi.org/10.14414/tiar.v4i01.280>
- Shakina, E., & Molodchik, M. (2014). Intangible-driven value creation: Supporting and obstructing factors. *Measuring Business Excellence*, 18(3), 87–100. <https://doi.org/10.1108/MBE-12-2013-0063>
- Shakina, E., Molodchik, M., & Barajas, A. (2017). Endogenous value creation: managerial decisions on intangibles. *Management Research Review*, 40(4), 410–428. <https://doi.org/10.1108/MRR-01-2016-0026>
- Siahaan, F. O. P. (2013). The Effect of Good Corporate Governance Mechanism, Leverage, and Firm Size on Firm Value. *GSTF Journal on Business Review*, 2(4), 71–79. <https://doi.org/10.5176/2010-4804>
- Simamora, A. J. (2022). Crime rate, real earnings management and managerial

- ability. *Corporate Governance (Bingley)*, 22(2), 405–423. <https://doi.org/10.1108/CG-02-2021-0079>
- Sisdianto, E., Razimi, M. S. A., Masykur, R., Mei Sari, R. D., & Robiansyah, A. (2023). The Effect of Environmental Performance on Financial Performance with Islamic Corporate Social Responsibility (ICSR) as Intervening Variable. *Jurnal Ilmiah Akuntansi*, 8(1), 191–205. <https://doi.org/10.23887/jia.v8i1.52442>
- Sumunar, K. I., & Anita. (2022). CEO overconfidence, audit fee, and audit report lag. *Jurnal Ilmu Sosial Dan Pendidikan*, 6(4), 2849–2861. <https://doi.org/10.36312/jisip.v6i4.4184/http>
- Susbiyani, A., Halim, M., & Animah, A. (2022). Determinants of Islamic social reporting disclosure and its effect on firm's value. *Journal of Islamic Accounting and Business Research*, 416–435. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JIABR-10-2021-0277>
- Suwardi, E., & Saragih, A. H. (2023). The effect of tax risk on audit report delay: Empirical evidence from Indonesia. *Cogent Business and Management*, 10(1). <https://doi.org/10.1080/23311975.2023.2192315>
- Swanson, Z., & Zhang, Y. (2018). Do covenant violations affect audit report timeliness? *International Journal of Accounting, Auditing and Performance Evaluation*, 14(1), 1–23. <https://doi.org/10.1504/IJAPE.2018.089399>
- Tarigan, J., Hatane, S. E., Stacia, L., & Widjaja, D. C. (2019). Corporate social responsibility policies and value creation: Does corporate governance and profitability mediate that relationship? *Investment Management and Financial Innovations*, 16(2), 270–280. [https://doi.org/10.21511/imfi.16\(2\).2019.23](https://doi.org/10.21511/imfi.16(2).2019.23)
- Tenggono, G. I. F., Lasdi, L., & Kristina, N. (2023). The Effect of Corporate Governance Mechanism on Company Value with Earnings Quality as Mediation. In *Proceedings of the 4th Asia Pacific Management Research Conference (APMRC 2022)*. <https://doi.org/10.2991/978-94-6463-076-3>
- Titman, S., & Trueman, B. (1986). Information quality and the valuation of new issues. *Journal of Accounting and Economics*, 8(2), 159–172. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0165-4101\(86\)90016-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/0165-4101(86)90016-9)
- Toumi, F., Khlif, H., & Khelil, I. (2022). National culture and audit report lag: cross-country investigation. *Journal of Economic and Administrative Sciences*. <https://doi.org/10.1108/jeas-03-2022-0066>
- Toumi, N., Benkraiem, R., & Hamrouni, A. (2016). Board director disciplinary and cognitive influence on corporate value creation. *Corporate Governance (Bingley)*, 16(3), 564–578. <https://doi.org/10.1108/CG-09-2015-0123>
- Vig, S., & Datta, M. (2021). The impact of corporate governance on sustainable value creation: A case of selected Indian firms. *Journal of Sustainable Finance and Investment*, 0(0), 1–19. <https://doi.org/10.1080/20430795.2021.1923337>
- Villanueva-Villar, M., Rivo-López, E., & Lago-Peñas, S. (2016). On the relationship between corporate governance and value creation in an economic crisis: Empirical evidence for the Spanish case. *BRQ Business Research Quarterly*, 19(4), 233–245. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.brq.2016.06.002>
- Waheed, A., & Mahmood, H. (2022). Corporate governance, litigation risk and firm performance: a mediation moderating model. *International Journal of*

- Emerging Markets*. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJOEM-02-2022-0320>
- Wanigasekara W.A.D.K.J., Weligamage S.S., & Karunarathne W.V.A.D. (2019). Measuring Value Creation: Combination of Financial Value Drivers and Non-Financial Value Drivers: a Literature Review. *Journal of Accounting and Finance*, 05(1), 22–41.
- Welch, J. (2019). The Volkswagen recovery: leaving scandal in the dust. *Journal of Business Strategy*, 40(2), 3–13. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JBS-04-2018-0068>
- Welch, J. (2023). Wells Fargo: a corporate recovery model to bank on. *Journal of Business Strategy*, 44(5), 247–256. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JBS-03-2022-0045>
- Wellalage, N. H., Kumar, V., Hunjra, A. I., & Al-Faryan, M. A. S. (2022). Environmental performance and firm financing during COVID-19 outbreaks: Evidence from SMEs. *Finance Research Letters*, 47(PA), 102568. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.frl.2021.102568>
- Widharma, F., & Susilowati, E. (2020). Auditor Switching, Financial Distress, And Financial Statement Fraud Practices With Audit Report Lag As Intervening Variable. *Journal of Accounting and Strategic Finance*, 3(2), 243–257.
- Winarto, J. (2015). The Determinants of Manufacturer Firm Value in Indonesia Stock Exchange. *International Journal of Information, Business and Management*, 7(4), 323. http://ijibm.site666.com/IJIBM_Vol7No4_Nov2015.pdf#page=206
- Wright, P., & Ferris, S. P. (1997). Agency conflict and corporate strategy: The effect of divestment on corporate value. *Strategic Management Journal*, 18(1), 77–83. [https://doi.org/10.1002/\(sici\)1097-0266\(199701\)18:1<77::aid-smj810>3.3.co;2-i](https://doi.org/10.1002/(sici)1097-0266(199701)18:1<77::aid-smj810>3.3.co;2-i)
- Wu, W., Peng, F., Shan, Y. G., & Zhang, L. (2020). Litigation risk and firm performance: The effect of internal and external corporate governance. *Corporate Governance An International Review*, 28(4), 1–30. <https://doi.org/10.1111/corg.12319>
- Yasin, F. M., & Nelson, S. P. (2012). Audit Committee and Internal Audit: *International Journal of Economics, Management and Accounting*, 20(2), 187–218.
- Yudianto, I., Mulyani, S., Fahmi, M., & Winarningsih, S. (2021). The influence of enterprise risk management implementation and internal audit quality on universities performance in Indonesia. *Journal of Southwest Jiaotong University*, 56(2), 193–217. <https://doi.org/10.35741/issn.0258-2724.56.2.13>
- Yusnia, V., & Kanti, A. (2021). Factors that Influence the Audit Report Lag Among Non-Financial Companies in Indonesia Stock Exchange. *Proceedings of the Ninth International Conference on Entrepreneurship and Business Management (ICEBM 2020)*, 174(Icebm 2020), 135–143. <https://doi.org/10.2991/aebmr.k.210507.021>
- Zeitun, R., & Saleh, A. S. (2015). Dynamic performance, financial leverage and financial crisis: Evidence from GCC countries. *EuroMed Journal of Business*, 10(2), 147–162. <https://doi.org/10.1108/EMJB-08-2014-0022>
- Zhao, X., Lynch, J. G., & Chen, Q. (2010). Reconsidering Baron and Kenny: Myths and truths about mediation analysis. *Journal of Consumer Research*, 37(2), 197–206. <https://doi.org/10.1086/651257>

- Zhou, Y., Liu, J., & Lei, D. (2022). The effect of financial reporting regimes on audit report lags and audit fees: evidence from firms cross-listed in the USA. *Journal of Financial Reporting and Accounting*.
<https://doi.org/10.1108/JFRA-09-2021-0261>
- Zoni, L., & Pippo, F. (2017). CFO and finance function: What matters in value creation. *Journal of Accounting and Organizational Change*, 13(2), 216–238.
<https://doi.org/10.1108/JAOC-12-2014-0059>